

CFD simulations over launch vehicle in the presence of umbilical tower at liftoff

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Abstract

It is important to assess the aerodynamic loads over launch vehicle while it is standing at the launch pad. Presence of umbilical tower affects the local flow-field over the launch vehicle. To assess the loads and flow-field around the vehicle, CFD simulations have been carried out at various wind plane angles. Open-source CFD code SU² has been used to carry out the simulations. Conventional convective flux discretization schemes leads to inaccuracies for low speed flow computations. AUSM+ -up scheme has been implemented in the SU² code to improve the accuracy for low speed flow conditions. Flow field is analyzed in detail and results are compared with the test data.

Keywords: CFD, SU², AUSM+ -up, Launch vehicle, ParaView

Nomenclature

M	Mach number	SdC_s/dx	Yaw plane load distribution
α	Angle of attack	C_p	Pressure coefficient
C_A	Axial force coefficient	SU ²	Stanford University Unstructured
C_N	Normal force coefficient	SA	Spalart Allamaras Turbulence model
X_{CP}	Center of pressure	SST	Shear Stress Transport Turbulence model
SdC_N/dx	Pitch plane load distribution	AUSM	Advection Upstream Splitting Method
Φ	Wind plane angle		

Introduction

It is important to assess the ground wind loads over launch vehicle as vehicle is in the vicinity of umbilical tower during liftoff phase. Also the vehicle sits on strapon support rings (SSR) at launch pedestal without anchoring. This makes the assessment of loads and moments coming over the vehicle essential for the high speed wind conditions. In the present work, numerical simulations have been carried out over a typical launch vehicle configuration in the presence of Umbilical Tower (UT) for the ground wind conditions. Aim of this study is to analyze the effect of the presence of UT over the flow-field as well as to assess the aerodynamic loads over the launch vehicle for these conditions.

Simulations have been carried out over wind tunnel force model of the launch vehicle. The model simulates all major protrusions. An unstructured hybrid mesh over this model has been generated using Pointwise, a commercial grid generation software [1]. Meshing of this geometry posed significant challenges as launch vehicle contains various protrusions varying in size and scale. This demanded considerable time and efforts for the mesh generation over the entire vehicle. Figure 1a shows geometry (launch vehicle sitting over MLP in the presence of UT) used in the simulations. Figure 1b and 1c shows mesh for cut section in two different planes of the vehicle sitting over the Mobile Launch Pedestal (MLP). First cell size is kept small enough to ensure $y^+ \sim 1$. More than 30 prism layers are generated close to the wall in order to resolve the boundary layer.

Figure-1a, 1b, 1c Geometry of Wind Tunnel model used for simulations and cut section showing mesh in two different planes

Code used for the simulations

Open-source CFD code SU² has been used to carry out the simulations [2, 3]. It uses median dual scheme for Finite Volume discretization and can handle structured as well as unstructured grid with mixed elements. SU² can employ either explicit or implicit time marching schemes and has SA and SST turbulence models [4, 5] to deal with variety of turbulent flow problems. Code is written using Object Oriented Programming concept in C++, which allows good flexibility of adding new capabilities and improving the existing capabilities. In the present work, free-stream velocity is very low (Mach number ~ 0.17). For the standard compressible flow solvers, numerical dissipation does not scale properly as Mach number approaches to zero [6]. This results in increasingly inaccurate results in the limit of Mach number tending to zero.

a) Validation

Keeping the above in mind, AUSM+ -up scheme [7] has been implemented in this code for carrying out low speed flow simulations more accurately. This scheme is extension of AUSM+ (Advection Upstream Splitting Method +) scheme [8] where pressure diffusion term is added in the interface Mach number term and velocity diffusion is added in the interface pressure term. This leads to improved scaling of numerical dissipation in low Mach number limit resulting in improved accuracy. While in conventional schemes, accuracy deteriorates as Mach number tends to zero. Complete details for implementation can be found in reference 7.

An exercise has been carried out over NACA-0012 airfoil at Mach number 0.1, angle of attack 1° (Euler simulation) to test the implementation. Figure 2 shows Cp palettes for stagnation region of NACA airfoil with various schemes. It can be clearly observed that AUSM+ -up gives better results as contours in stagnation region are smooth and physical in comparison to other schemes like JST [9], Roe [10] and HLLC [11]. Also value of stagnation Cp is much closer to 1.0 for AUSM+ -up scheme in comparison to other schemes.

Figure-2 pressure contours in stagnation region of NACA airfoil ($M=0.1$, $\alpha=1^\circ$)

Results and Discussion

One can use empirical methods like cross flow theory, experiments or CFD to generate the loads over the vehicle for these conditions. But empirical methods have their own limitations like simplifying assumptions for example accounting the presence of UT etc. On the other hand, experiments are costly hence CFD is a good choice to generate the aerodynamic data including load distribution. Keeping this in mind, it was decided to carry out CFD simulations over the launch vehicle in absence and presence of UT for the ground wind conditions. Simulations have been carried out for 60 m/sec wind velocity at various wind plane angles ($\Phi = -270^\circ, -180^\circ$ and -90°). Figure 3 also shows the coordinate system and sign convention used in the simulations (adopted from the convention of wind tunnel tests).

Figure-3 Coordinate system used for the simulations

a) Convergence monitoring

Convergence for all the cases have been ensured by monitoring forces and moments with respect to the iterations. Figure 4 shows the convergence plot for C_N and X_{CPN} for wind plane angle -180° deg case simulation (vehicle is in presence of UT). Simulations have been run for sufficient number of iterations to ensure the convergence. Convergence is monitored for all the cases in similar manner.

It is observed that finally the coefficients become oscillatory. A mean of last five cycles or last few thousands of iterations has been taken and given as the steady state value.

Figure-4 Convergence plot for C_N and X_{CPN} ($\Phi = -180^\circ$)

Aerodynamic coefficients obtained from the simulation results have been compared with the wind tunnel test data. For wind plane angles -270° and -180° , simulation data matches within 6% of the test data. While for other wind plane angles -225° and -315° , differences of 18-24% are observed in the aerodynamic coefficients. Overall a reasonable match between the tunnel data and CFD is observed.

b) Effect of Umbilical Tower

Presence of UT can considerably alter the effective wind plane angle than that would have been in the absence of UT for certain range of free stream wind plane angle. This can be observed from the simulation results ($\Phi = -270$ deg case). Figure 5 presents velocity vector plot in xz plane for wind plane angle -270° case, flow deflection towards the vehicle can be clearly seen. This shifts the stagnation region on the vehicle, resulting in normal force which otherwise would have been negligible. Open-source software ParaView [12] has been used for carrying out the post-processing.

Figures 6 and 7 show yaw and pitch plane load distribution over core, P+ strapon, P- strapon as well as complete vehicle at $\Phi -270$ deg. Here since P- strapon is directly facing the flow, side force is higher on this in comparison to P+ strapon. Deflection of flow in the presence of UT also generates normal force on the vehicle This can be clearly observed from the pitch plane load distribution plot presented in Figure 7.

Figure-5 Velocity vector plot in XY plane showing deflection of flow in presence of UT (Vehicle, MLP and UT are colored with Cp)

Figure-6 Yaw plane load distribution for $\Phi = -270^\circ$ case

Figure-7 Pitch plane load distribution for $\Phi = -270^\circ$ case

The comparison of load distribution on strapon is shown in Figure 8 for $\Phi -270^\circ$ case. One can clearly see the effect of presence of UT in normal force load distribution for the windward strapon. Changes in leeward side strapons are very small. While for $\Phi -225^\circ$ case, only minor differences in load distribution is observed for the wind ward strapon as approaching flow direction is not considerably altered by the UT (as it is behind the vehicle) in this case (Figure 9). With this study, it can be conjectured that effect of UT prevails in 1st and 4th quadrants.

Figure 8 - Comparison of load distribution for windward strapon $\Phi -270^\circ$ case

Figure-9 Load distribution over windward and leeward strapons for Φ -225° case

Conclusion

Numerical simulations have been carried out to assess the ground wind loads over launch vehicle and to study the effect of presence of umbilical tower. An unstructured hybrid mesh, which can resolve flow to the wall, has been generated over the launch vehicle configuration. Open-source CFD code SU² has been used for carrying out the simulations. AUSM+ -up scheme has been implemented in this code to carry out simulation for this low speed flow conditions. This scheme resulted in improved accuracy as well as increased robustness (solution with other schemes were blowing out after few thousand iterations) for the simulations of this problem. Flow-field obtained from the simulations is analyzed and data is compared with the test data. Detailed insight of the flow-field as well as aero data has been gained from this analysis.

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